

EDUCATION POLICY AND MODERNIZATION STAGE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the educational policy of Uzbekistan and the ongoing reforms in this area. Normative documents in the field of higher education, laws, decrees and the essence of the concept of education development are analyzed. The existing problems in this area of higher education are also scientifically justified.

Key words: globalization, higher education, law on education, concept, competitive specialist, international rating.

Аннотация. Мақолада Ўзбекистоннинг таълим соҳасидаги давлат сиёсати ва ушбу йўналишда амалга оширилаётган ислохотлар ёритилган. Олий таълим тизимидаги меъёрий ҳужжатлар: қонунлар, фармонлар ва Ўзбекистон Республикаси олий таълим тизими-ни 2030 йилгача ривожлантириш концепциясининг аҳамияти ва моҳияти таҳлил қилинган. Шунингдек, мамлакатимиз олий таълим тизимида мавжуд муаммолар илмий жиҳатдан асослаб берилган.

Калит сўзлар: глобаллашув, олий таълим, таълимга оид қонун, концепция, рақобатбардош мутахассис, халқаро рейтинг.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена образовательной политике Узбекистана и проводимым реформам в этой области. Проанализированы нормативные документы, регламентирующие сферу высшего образования, законы, указы и суть концепции развития образования, а также существующие проблемы в этой области.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, высшее образование, закон об образовании, концепция, конкурентоспособный специалист, международный рейтинг.

Introduction

While the modern era of globalization vests new demands on the organization, management and content of education, especially the higher education system, the Higher Education System must also meet the requirements of the uncertain processes of globalization and the rapid technological and information development of society. There is no doubt that the creation of a new concept of education in the higher education system of our country and the effective use of not only traditional but also innovative approaches

and interaction in teaching and educating young people on the basis of modern knowledge will yield the expected results.

The essence of the new state policy of Uzbekistan in the field of education is to ensure the priority of education as the most intellectually potential “sector” of the economy. The main goal of the state policy in the field of higher education is to form an adequate model of education that meets all the challenges of the XXI century, to recognize the leading role of society in the formation of a new Uzbekistan. This requires

a special responsibility from the state and society for the current state of education, the effectiveness of its modernization, the preservation of the best traditions and standards of the classical world's higher education system.

Discussion

We can see from the views and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev that the modernization of education in Uzbekistan is now officially recognized as the main strategic line of state policy in the field of education in Uzbekistan. This, of course, requires further improvement of the higher vocational education system in Uzbekistan. First, one of the most visible results of innovative changes in education, in our opinion, is the acceleration of the "aging" of knowledge acquired in the process of studying at the university, as well as the incompatibility of theoretical knowledge with the needs of practical life. Accordingly, there is a growing need to constantly update and put this knowledge into practice. In this regard, the transition of the education system of the country to a two-tier system (introduction of bachelor's degree) has become a necessity for all areas to unite specialists in practice and further development of science. Radical improvement of education policy and further strengthening of the legal framework in this area leads to its integration into international educational standards. Preparations for Uzbekistan's accession to the Bologna Convention have highlighted the need to create a single educational space and, accordingly, adherence to the same European standards for quality of education, uniform technological and humanitarian standards, and training of specialists in all fields.

Second, the existence of a single professional qualification in the field of education, not only in Uzbekistan, but in the whole of Europe, has led to a complete change in a number of parameters required for bachelors in social sciences and humanities, including language, culture, economics, politics, etc. was the formation of the necessary professional and general cultural competencies of future professionals occur against the background of significant changes not only in the forms, levels, but also in the content of the edu-

cational process. For example, a distinctive feature of the modern education system is the transition from the formation of educational content by the state to the introduction of new aspects and participants in this system, in particular, employers¹. At the same time, this approach helps to train competitive professionals in the modern labor market at all levels, expands the possibility of influencing the content, forms and methods of organizing the educational process, and even helps to choose the type of educational institution. On the one hand, this approach helps to train professionals of all levels who are competitive in the modern labor market. In fact, these parameters affect the quality of education to one degree or two.

The implementation of the modern paradigm of vocational education today, its effectiveness and quality depends mainly on the presence of a formed professional consciousness, the success of the formation of the general culture and professional skills required in future professionals. However, it is known that these are not the only indicators of the quality of education. It is no coincidence that in modern world practice, different conceptual and practical approaches are used to assess the quality of work of higher education institutions in the training of specialists for different fields. Among them, attention, effective and general approaches can be noted.

According to world researchers, a reputation-based approach to assessing the professional level of educational programs and educational institutions usually uses an expert mechanism. Effective, on the contrary, is based on the measurement of quantitative indicators of university activity. The general approach is based on the principles of "universal quality management" (TOQM) and the requirements of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). These approaches are available within two historically formed quality assessment models: English and French². The first is based on the internal self-esteem of the university academic community. In France, it is based on the external evaluation of the university in terms of its responsibility to society and the state.

In general, there is no single system of institutional evaluation of university performance in Europe. Here, each country has its own approach to ensuring and

¹ Kesaeva R.E., Byazrova T.T., Kantemirova-Kanukova G.A. Modernization of the system of higher professional education in Russia // Fundamental research. – 2014. – № 9-6. – P. 94.

² www.lex.uz. April 29, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree. No. UP-5987

evaluating the quality of higher education. The main elements of the quality assessment system in Uzbekistan are standardization, licensing, certification and accreditation of educational institutions. However, the basis for quality assessment is, first and foremost, the State Education Standards and State Requirements. Educational standards in the higher education institutions of Uzbekistan include the requirements for all components of the educational process, including personnel, teaching methods, logistics and information equipment.

With all the differences in approaches to the problem of ensuring the level and effectiveness of education, Uzbekistan today pays maximum attention to the quality of education in terms of its participation in the Bologna process. A number of normative and legal acts adopted in recent years confirm this. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Concept of Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education of September 23, 2020, PD No.637, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2020 No.5987, 2016-2025 it is sufficient to refer to key documents such as the education development target program.

The most important task of the higher education system is, first of all, to improve the quality of education, to ensure its validity, continuity and adequacy to the needs of modern society and the state. It is important to ensure the availability of quality education that meets the requirements of innovative socially oriented development of Uzbekistan, as well as modernize general and preschool education as an institution of social development, adapt the content and structure of vocational education to the needs of the labor market, develop education quality assessment and demand for educational services. Does the concept of long-term socio-economic development of Uzbekistan until 2025 emphasize the priority of higher education?

In this regard, it should be noted that over the past decades, Uzbekistan's transition to a system of market relations, the intensity and dynamism of modern social processes in society have qualitatively changed not only the socio-structural relations in various spheres of Uzbekistan. There are new forms of education in our country, which ensure the effectiveness of the process of preservation, reproduction and subsequent

inculcation of professional knowledge, cultural, historical and moral values in society. It changes social consciousness, which places high demands not only on masters but also on bachelors in all fields on professional and general cultural competencies. In recent years, the list of indicators of the quality of education has expanded significantly. Today, university status is determined only by traditional indicators. There plays an important role the existence of basic educational programs in the higher education system such as: student training regimes, postgraduate and additional vocational education programs, the level of participation of students at all levels in research activities, the existence of a system of employment of graduates in higher education, continuing education and university graduates' spectra such as training opportunities and so on.

However, we find that these processes are highly contradictory, sometimes damaging to the traditions of the national classical education system, and aspirations such as achieving proportionality in efforts to meet the requirements of the European education system may not always be justified. In this regard, while limiting their social status, the maximum expansion of the field of professional activity of bachelors is prepared for a new generation of socio-technological, organizational-managerial, research and socio-project activities. The professional qualifications of bachelors in these fields of activity, in our opinion, maximize the professional differences between bachelor and master and deprive the bachelor of the relevant status. Many issues related to the modernization of education and its outcomes have not been addressed yet. Modernization of the higher education system will allow to see some miscalculations in the process of modernization and implementation of the new system of quality assessment of education. At the same time, effective work is being done to develop and implement basic skills-based curricula for all levels of education related to the new Legislation in the field of education. One of the most important indicators of the quality of education in terms of a qualified approach is the implementation of work focused on practical results.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of October 8, 2019 No.5847, by 2030 at least 10 higher education institutions in the country will be included in the first 1000 places in the ranking of internationally recognized organiza-

tions (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities). It is planned to include in the list of educational institutions, including the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University, a list of the top 500 higher education institutions, including the development of an action plan for the introduction of modern mechanisms of state support for these institutions.

The concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 is based on the needs of the social sphere and the economy, improving the quality of education, training competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities, international cooperation. It is also developed in pursuance of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of July 11, 2019 No.4391 "On measures to introduce new management principles in the system of higher and secondary special education". The concept defines the strategic goals, priorities, objectives, medium and long-term stages of development of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan and is the basis for the development of programs and comprehensive measures in this area. Today, there are 114 higher education institutions in the country, of which 93 are local and 21 are foreign higher education institutions and their branches. In particular, 6 new higher education institutions, 17 branches and 14 branches of foreign higher education institutions have been established in the last 3 years³. Based on the proposals of personnel customers, the classification of higher education areas and specialties included 329 areas of education and 582 master's specialties. In the 2019/2020 academic year, part-time education was introduced in 59 higher education institutions, and evening education was introduced in 10 higher education institutions.

The number of students studying in higher educational institutions of the country amounted to 410 thousand in the bachelor's degree and 13 thousand in the master's degree, which has increased 1.7 times over the past 3 years. 54.8% of students are in the humanities and pedagogy, 25.2% in production and technology, 5.2% in the social sphere, economics and law, 5.9% in agriculture and water management, 4.4% in health and social care, 4, 5% are studying in the field

of education and specialties in the field of service education. 40.8% of master's students are in the humanities and pedagogy, 23.3% in production and technology, 13.3% in the social sphere, economics and law, 5.9% in agriculture and water management, 13.5% in healthcare and social security, 3.2% are studying in the field of service education.

The admission parameters for the 2019/2020 academic year amounted to 121,000 and increased by 18% compared to the previous year and by 92% compared to 2016. Starting from the 2018/2019 academic year, 16 higher education institutions of the country have launched training activities on the basis of joint educational programs in cooperation with foreign higher education institutions. Today, the number of academic councils awarding academic degrees in higher education institutions is 84 (48 in 2017). As a result of the defense of doctoral dissertations by 1693 professors and teachers in the last 3 years, the number of pedagogical staff with academic degrees in higher education institutions reached 9636 (including 2130 doctors of sciences (DSc), 7506 candidates of sciences (PhD) and scientific potential of higher educational institutions of the republic. An increase of 1 percent. Over the past 3 years, 1,611 professors and teachers of higher education institutions have been provided with internships and advanced training in foreign higher education institutions. Within the framework of international cooperation, 112 young people were admitted to master's and 51 to doctoral programs at foreign universities and research institutions.

The "El-Yurt Umidi" Foundation provided internships for 46 professors and teachers in Canada, the United Kingdom and Italy, and involved 1,154 highly qualified foreign teachers and scientists in the educational process in 2017-2019 (94 from the United States and 445 from Europe) as a result of reforms in this area, such as the increase in the base salary of professors with doctoral degrees in higher education institutions by 3.9 times compared to 2016. At the same time, the higher education system still faces a number of pressing problems and shortcomings in the training of highly qualified personnel in this area, including: the low level of coverage with higher education; ineffective work on training in cooperation with higher education institutions and customers, insufficient par-

³ www.lex.uz. April 29, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree. No. UP-5987.

ticipation of employers in the formation of the content of higher education; the level of qualification of the trained specialists does not meet the modern requirements of the labor market; the fact that the professional skills of professors and teachers lag behind today's requirements due to the low level of mastery of foreign languages and information and communication technologies; work on improving the quality of textbooks, the use of foreign literature as additional or alternative textbooks is not sufficiently organized; lack of mechanisms for selection of talented young people for higher education institutions; These include the ineffectiveness of the system of professional development of teachers, the need to strengthen the spiritual and moral content of higher education, the education of young people in the spirit of patriotism, respect for national values, humanism and high spiritual ideas, strengthening immunity against foreign ideas and ideologies.

As noted in the concept, the commercialization of scientific developments in the field of research and innovation, the involvement of talented young people in research is insufficient, and a strong integration of education, science and industry is not provided fully. Also, the scientific potential of higher education institutions is only 36.4%, the average age of employees with academic degrees is 49 (doctors – 56 years, doctors of philosophy and candidates of science – 43 years), remains high, the share of retirees among doctors of science is 45 percent. There are no effective mechanisms to encourage the activities of professors, researchers and young scientists engaged in research.

Conclusion

In recent years, there is a need to do more to increase the attractiveness of higher education and ensure international competitiveness. In other words, since the higher education institutions of the republic are not included in the list of the first 1000 places in the ranking of internationally recognized organizations, their official websites are also not included in the list of 1000 places in the international ranking of Webometrics, educational programs and student assessment system are not adapted to international standards. Infrastructure facilities are not adapted to the needs of foreign students, advocacy work to attract foreigners to study in our country, including PR-projects (organization of days of higher education insti-

tutions of Uzbekistan, presentations, etc.) is insufficiently organized, the interactive virtual platform in international universities does not exist as it should. In the future, the Concept envisages the implementation of the following measures to expand the coverage of higher education, improve the quality of training of specialists with higher education: development of public-private partnership in higher education, state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions; creation of a competitive environment in higher education through the organization of the activities of branches of institutions; establishment of the Presidential University – a leading center of education and science, training highly qualified personal with modern knowledge and skills, independent thinking, patriotic, professional staff in accordance with international standards and national traditions; further strengthening the guarantees of women's right to higher education, ensuring the priority of the principles of gender equality in education, developing mechanisms for the transfer of curricula of higher education institutions to the credit-module system and their gradual transfer to this system; Systematic organization of spiritual and educational work in higher education institutions, aimed at increasing the effectiveness of measures taken in this area, raising the intellectual potential, thinking and worldview of young people, strengthening ideological immunity, upbringing as a harmoniously developed generation with a sense of patriotism and service to the people.

Development and implementation of the concept of development of spiritual and moral consciousness of young people; to train young people who are able to take responsibility for solving important tasks facing the state and society, who are patriotic, enterprising, have modern knowledge and skills, have human qualities as professionals, to use educational methods that require new approaches; universal awareness of the content of legislation, legal awareness and culture of young people, healthy lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, peace and interethnic harmony, freedom of conscience, respect for the languages, customs and traditions of all nations and peoples. We hope that along with the values, special attention will be paid to such aspects as the development of national and moral values, socio-political and economic activity, the formation of a strong civic position.